

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17353458

DIGITAL AND CULTURAL BOUNDARY INTEGRATION: PATHWAYS TO NURSES' LIFE SATISFACTION IN INDIA

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Received: 12/06/2025

Accepted: 18/09/2025

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ABSTRACT

The present study investigates the life satisfaction of nurses as they integrate digital and cultural boundaries in India, with family-to-work enrichment and job satisfaction portrayed as mediatory mechanisms. The study extends boundary theory by placing boundary management within the socio-cultural framework and ICT-intensive health care context. Utilizing a quantitative survey-based methodology, 200 valid responses were obtained from nurses located in Gorakhpur, Uttar Pradesh. The direct and indirect relationships were tested in JASP amongst boundary integration, family-to-work enrichment, job satisfaction, and life satisfaction. The results showed that boundary integration positively influenced family-to-work enrichment and job satisfaction, which, in turn, positively influenced life satisfaction. The mediation analyses further confirmed that family-to-work enrichment and job satisfaction serve as key mediators between boundary integration and life satisfaction. Therefore, the results suggest that boundary management between work and family is not just purely a psychological mechanism on the individual level, but a process conditioned by cultural caregiving responsibilities. Theory contribution included reframing boundary theory as culturally mediated and digitally mediated, while practical implications included implications for hospital administrators and policy makers to consider when designing workplace practices that support employees.

KEYWORDS: Cultural Boundaries, Socio-Cultural Norms, Job Satisfaction, Life Satisfaction, Nurses.

1. INTRODUCTION

The issue of navigating personal and professional life has long been an important problem for employees in every industry, and scholars have been researching the overlap between work and family roles for more than thirty years (Rosa, 2022). Traditionally, this issue has been cast as a psychological and organizational issue: how do individuals navigate boundaries in order to reduce conflict and increase productivity in both domains (Zhang, 2025). Despite numerous studies, the problem has not been resolved, implying the issue lies deeper than individual strategies (Marcionetti & Castelli, 2023).

Recently and especially during COVID-19, the boundaries between work and life have been transformed by digital transformation and cultural shifts (Mirbabaie & Marx, 2024). Remote and hybrid work models, which have emerged during and as a result of COVID-19, have led to new expectations of constant connectivity, blurred physical and temporal boundaries, and created shifting cultural narratives associated with work, family, and identity in general there has been a lot of discussion (Landolfi et al., 2021). Technology, together with telehealth platforms, electronic health records, mobile apps, and communication through online means, has shifted the dynamics of work and how family roles are negotiated, to being transactional, and often quite questionable (Poonsuph, 2022). At the interface as well, cultural expectations based on collectivism or individualism, and the division of labor based upon traditional gender roles or newer egalitarian roles continue to act as constraints on people in how they perceive and work through the work-family interface in their own lives (Lan & Feng, 2025).

In contrast, women professionals from the Global South perceive very nuanced pressures, being cultural in nature on the one hand and digital push factors on the other (Paludi & Krysa, 2023). Nursing practitioners provide a helpful illustration of this paradox: variability in their work hours, emotional work with considerable responsibility, limited time for a personal break (Pagnozzi et al., 2024). In addition, those make the phenomena worse today with more deeply root digital push factors of documentation, virtual tele-consultation, and ICT capacity-based reporting engagement, which continues to hold nursing practitioners and professions accountable from anywhere in the world, thus preventing any physical escape from the hospital or immediate clinical setting (Rainoldi et al., 2024). A very different story emerges as soon as we accept the voices of these women by no longer

discussing just one way of managing time but instead, a cultural and technologic interpretation of being a nurse, of being a caring practitioner, and of being a family member.

Even though we have shifted our discussions about workforce needs and organizational challenges in health care, there is little attention to the broad health and life satisfaction of women nurse practitioners (Deschênes, 2024). Most studies published on nursing still focus on organizational related outcomes such as productivity, retention and stress alleviation, without consideration of the sociolinguistic and digital context that facilitate or create particular work-life balance experiences (Petani & Mengis, 2023). According to Smith and Sinkford (2022), in collectivist society, such as India, family obligations may compel a higher expectation of contradictory or overlapping work availability, while technological capacity continues to encourage full engagement. Thus, nurses in such contexts face an intersection of global digital pressures and local cultural responsibilities, making them an especially important group for understanding boundary integration in the 21st century.

It can easily be shown that the boundary theory (Kreiner et al., 2006) is well suited for investigating these dynamics. It claims that people actively build and regulate the boundaries in work and non-work domains and those domains may vary in degrees of hard or soft segmentation. While applications of this theory is typically couched in a traditional sense when thinking about boundaries and preferences as a separable, individual psychological preference. By grounding boundary theory in the socio-cultural and technological micro-contexts structuring those personal choices, this study shifts scholarship in CMC in a new direction. That is, boundaries are not only a personal strategy, but they also reflect cultural constraints and digital systems which shape the feasibility of various strategies differently.

Life satisfaction (Ng et al., 2023) has become the indicator of overall wellbeing, not individual happiness. In this sense, family-to-work enrichment is an important process. FWE represents a positive spillover of family life resources, skills and emotional support to work (Goel et al., 2021). Job satisfaction is a similarly important mediating variable that links boundary management to life satisfaction. In combination, these perspectives resonate with the importance of examining boundary work of today's integration as a digitally mediated cultural experience (Paludi & Krysa, 2023). Life satisfaction is related not only to work-family hours trade-off, but overall hybrid cultural identities, digital expectations

and new social norms (Pan et al., 2021). Through a lens of examining nurses in India, this paper addresses an important gap by locating work-life balance within culture and technology intersectional frameworks, thereby providing a more complete understanding of well-being in the digital age.

The objectives of this study are threefold. First, to investigate the relationship between digital and cultural boundary integration and life satisfaction among female nurses. Second, to examine the mediating role of family-to-work enrichment in this relationship, emphasizing how cultural and digital adaptations within families enhance well-being. Third, to explore how job satisfaction mediates the association between boundary integration and life satisfaction in ICT-intensive healthcare contexts. By doing so, this research not only advances theoretical understanding of boundary theory but also contributes practical insights for policymakers, hospital administrators, and digital workplace designers seeking to improve employee and societal well-being.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES

2.1. Cross-Cultural Perspectives on Boundary Integration

Strategies for boundary integration (BI) differ greatly depending upon cultures. In collectivist cultures, where family roles are highlighted, boundaries are naturally more fluid and porous, resulting in a larger number of blended resources and expectations (Pagnozzi et al., 2024). In more individualist cultures, work and non-work life are less likely lead to a number of segmented approaches. Gender roles add another layer of complexity: in many cultures and contexts, women are often left carrying a larger share of family and household responsibilities which correlate with integration of the professional and family domains (Levänen et al., 2022). Nurses, a predominantly female profession globally, reflect this cultural dimension, which necessitate simultaneously following professional, family, and cultural expectations (Goel et al., 2021). From a cross-cultural perspective, BI also contributes to understanding that the outcomes of well-being satisfaction are not universal but are useful in understanding the ways in which societies shape our expectations of how we should behave in different areas of our life, and understanding our culturally defined scripts (Smith & Sinkford, 2022).

2.2. Digital Work, ICT, and Hybrid Cultures

The quick shift to digital methods for work has changed the very notion of boundaries (Rainoldi et

al., 2024). Communication and information technological devices such as Zoom, Slack, and electronic medical records are extending work deep into the home and permitting use of digital tethering that intervene into family time. The hybrid work expectation that was introduced by COVID-19 has led to an ecosystem of fuzzy boundaries and blocked the means for separation (Lan & Feng, 2025). Similarly, to nurses who can conduct telehealth visits, use mobile reporting systems, and conduct online shift handoffs. Although all of these methods may add efficiencies to work and opportunities for flexibility, they also create new expectations of availability and new emotional demands (Deschênes, 2024). When viewed within cultural contexts characterized by strong family caregiving norms, the new and old forms of work technologies, with/against pre-existing family responsibilities create new and overlapping dynamics to a work-life interface (Petani & Mengis, 2023). Thus, both organizational digital factors and culture factors are aligned to contribute to the extent to which boundary integration promote enrichment and satisfaction versus stress and dissatisfaction.

2.3. Hypotheses Development

Boundary integration (BI) is about how people navigate across the permeability of roles within work and family contexts, varying from separation to high integration (Tang et al., 2024). Traditionally, BI has been thought of as a personal orientation or strategy that individuals utilize to manage time and energy demands between multiple roles (De Gieter et al., 2022). When boundaries are successfully managed, individuals transfer resources and experiences from one domain to the other, benefitting work life and family life (Meng, 2022). However, BI is no longer a purely individual endeavor. In contemporary societies, BI is influenced by cultural expectations around collectivist or individualist values, gendered expectations, and technological structures that support our connection (Ng et al., 2022). For instance, in nursing work, nurses negotiate shifts but also live with a constant integrative obligation to ICT based reporting and telehealth work. Given this, BI must be reconceptualized as culturally mediated digital boundary management, to account for societal expectations and digital pressures (Kunkcu et al., 2024). Life satisfaction (LS) denotes overall subjective and satisfactory experiences across domains of life (Ng et al., 2023). Studies indicate that BI has a positive impact upon LS because it decreases stress and increases balance between personal and professional life (Pan et al., 2021). Hence, the following

hypotheses are proposed.

H1: Digital and Cultural Boundary Integration is positively associated with Life Satisfaction.

H2: Digital and Cultural Boundary Integration is positively associated with Job Satisfaction.

H3: Digital and Cultural Boundary Integration is positively associated with Family-to-Work Enrichment.

Family-to-Work Enrichment (FWE) is about the transfer of resources such as support, competencies, energy characterized as positive from family to work (Rashmi & Kataria, 2021). Enrichment occurs by virtue of strong family bonds that enable a worker to handle job demands more effectively, enhancing job performance and personal satisfaction (McDaniel et al., 2021). In the contemporary digital context, enrichment is dependent not only on emotional resources but also on families' responsiveness to technology-oriented work (Choi et al., 2022). Furthermore, households may reschedule responsibilities to facilitate late-night telehealth appointments with patients or encourage the family to share use of devices and enact responsibilities jointly related to work obligations (Chughtai, 2021). In living in affirmative, collectivistic contexts, sometimes family members become even more directly involved in enabling job performance, which ultimately increases the richness of the FWE process (Orellana et al., 2023). Thus, FWE can also be understood as a cultural adaptation process to technology demands and hybrid jobs. Hence, the following hypotheses are proposed.

H4: Family-to-Work Enrichment is positively associated with Life Satisfaction.

H6: Family-to-Work Enrichment mediates the relationship between Digital and Cultural Boundary Integration and Life Satisfaction.

Job satisfaction (JS) is defined as a favorable emotional reaction to their job derived from evaluating experiences, environmental conditions, and to a certain extent, workplace resources (Aruldoss et al., 2020). JS has typically been viewed as related to job elements and support systems but has been found to be consistent predictor of life satisfaction (Şimşek Demirbağ & Demirbağ, 2022). In digital and hybrid workplaces however, satisfaction is highly contingent on the adoption of ICT tools into the job, managing the demands of digital workplaces, and cultural expectations of availability (García-Salirrosas et al., 2023). In the nurses' case, satisfaction can stem from status and completing their professional work duties, as well as successfully negotiating digital demands, such as electronic reporting and teleconsultation, while satisfying their caregiving duties to families (Michel et al., 2022). In

sum, JS not only represents progression of well-being at work, but is also a cultural and technological negotiation of modern working (Palumbo et al., 2021). Hence, the following hypotheses are proposed. H5: Job Satisfaction is positively associated with Life Satisfaction.

H7: Job Satisfaction mediates the relationship between Digital and Cultural Boundary Integration and Life Satisfaction.

The research model of this study is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Research Model.

3. METHODOLOGY

This research utilized a quantitative survey design to examine how digital and cultural boundary integration affects life satisfaction with family-to-work enrichment and job satisfaction functioning as mediators. Choosing to study nurses in Gorakhpur, Uttar Pradesh, India, was a practical yet theoretical choice. As a profession, nurses occupy a different and distinct space at the nexus of extreme work-related demands, traditional cultural caregiving roles, and increasing use of information and communication technologies, including electronic health records, telehealth platforms, etc. As a result, their experiences became the most appropriate to examine how individual choices and macro cultural norms and ICT infrastructure are structuring work-life boundaries.

We conducted a survey using a structured questionnaire we administered to nurses working in public and private hospitals in Gorakhpur. Employing purposive sampling ensured that respondents were currently delivering direct care with regular exposure to ICT-enabled hospital systems. Of the 500 questionnaires we distributed, we received 283 in return but only 200 were deemed suitable for analysis. The sample size satisfied the required levels for structural equation modeling and was sufficient to test the proposed relationships. The survey addressed the four main constructs boundary integration, family-to-work enrichment, job satisfaction, and life satisfaction, while it included questions to reflect the cultural and technological contexts. This included questions about digital work

tasks like online managing shift rotation, teleconsulting patients, and mobile reporting and questions to address family expectations and caretaking responsibilities rooted in the collectivist culture.

Boundary integration was assessed with seven items adapted by Matthews and Barnes-Farrell (2010). Adjustments were made to assess boundary integration into the context of digital connectivity, for example, availability via mobile devices or the integration of electronic records into personal routines. Family-to-work enrichment was assessed with six items from Fisher *et al.* (2009) that were adapted to reflect context where family was involved in adapting to the digital workloads, such as feeling supported emotionally while online or sharing technology for working at home. Job satisfaction was measured with five items, adapting the original items to include satisfaction with ICT systems as well as organizational support of hybrid work practices to fit the context of the analysis framework. Life satisfaction was assessed with the well-cited Satisfaction with Life Scale (Pavot & Diener, 2008). Each of the items used a 5-point Likert-type scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Reliability was acceptable for all measures (Cronbach's alpha = 0.74 to 0.88) and confirmatory factor analysis indicated strong construct validity.

Before the main survey took place, a pilot test of the questionnaire was conducted with 60 nurses in order to enhance clarity and ensure cultural relevance and relevance to the digital work context. Based on the feedback, minimal changes were made to the wording, particularly to ensure that items successfully captured both the demands of caregiving cultures and ICT professional demands. Content validity was strengthened through input from hospital administrators and subject matter experts in organizational psychology and cultural studies to ensure that the instrument was appropriate for measuring psychological and socio-cultural factors of the work-life interface.

The final dataset was analyzed using SPSS 25 and JASP (Murad *et al.*, 2025). Descriptive statistics were first produced to characterize the sample, followed by confirmatory factor analysis to assess reliability, convergent validity, and discriminant validity. Next, structural equation modeling was used to analyze whether boundary integration, family-to-work enrichment, job satisfaction, and life satisfaction were related in hypothesized ways, including the proposed mediating effects. Mediation analysis with bootstrapping procedures was used to estimate indirect effects and confidence intervals.

Additionally, to demonstrate that common method variance was not a concern for this study, both procedural and statistical remedies were followed as recommended. Respondents were assured of anonymity, item wording was altered to constrain consistency bias, and correlation coefficients were inspected to ensure that none were above common thresholds 0.9, thereby confirming that common method variance was not a concern.

3.1. Data Analysis and Findings

The findings of this study were investigated from the perspective of descriptive statistics at first. The study found that all 200 responses were valid, and there was 0 missing value in it. Furthermore, the mean value and standard deviation was investigated. A mean is a quantity representing the center of a collection of numbers and is intermediate to the extreme values of the set of numbers. While the standard deviation is a measure of the amount of variation of the values of a variable about its mean. The mean value was ± 3 which is considered significant when a 5-point Likert scale is used to collect the data (Hair *et al.*, 2011). In accordance, the standard deviation value for each variable was near to 1 which was also considered as significant. Hence, the normality of the data was confirmed during this analysis. The findings of descriptive statistics are reported in Table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics.

Variable	Boundary Integration	Family to Work Enrichment	Job Satisfaction	Life Satisfaction
Valid	200	200	200	200
Missing	0	0	0	0
Mean	3.038	3.984	3.158	3.038
Std. Deviation	1.096	0.986	1.039	1.091

The study further checked the findings of Pearson' correlation. Pearson correlation measures the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two continuous variables, represented by a coefficient ranging from -1 to +1. A value of +1

indicates a perfect positive linear relationship, -1 indicates a perfect negative linear relationship, and 0 indicates no linear relationship. It is a parametric test that requires variables to be normally distributed and suitable for interval or ratio data. The findings

presented in Table 2 highlighted that p value for all variables correlations was <.001. Hence, the Pearson'

correlation was accepted in this study, and significant correlation was reported in data.

Table 2: Pearson Correlation.

Variables		Pearson's r	p
Boundary Integration	Family to Work Enrichment	0.829	< .001
Boundary Integration	Job Satisfaction	0.767	< .001
Boundary Integration	Life Satisfaction	0.825	< .001
Family to Work Enrichment	Job Satisfaction	0.807	< .001
Family to Work Enrichment	Life Satisfaction	0.833	< .001
Job Satisfaction	Life Satisfaction	0.809	< .001

The study at third investigated the relationship between variables. The findings highlighted that family to work enrichment has a significant impact on life satisfaction (<.001). Furthermore, the study also found that job satisfaction has a significant impact on life satisfaction (<.001). In accordance with these findings, the study also confirmed that

boundary integration has a significant impact on life satisfaction (<.001). Meanwhile, the impact of boundary integration was also significant on family to work enrichment (<.001) and job satisfaction (<.001). The findings of direct paths are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Direct Paths.

Paths	Estimate	Std. error	z-value	p
Family to Work Enrichment → Life Satisfaction	0.345	0.078	4.419	< .001
Job Satisfaction → Life Satisfaction	0.312	0.065	4.837	< .001
Boundary Integration → Life Satisfaction	0.337	0.065	5.224	< .001
Boundary Integration → Family to Work Enrichment	0.746	0.037	20.061	< .001
Boundary Integration → Job Satisfaction	0.726	0.045	16.15	< .001

Finally, the findings of indirect paths were checked and are reported in Table 4 and Figure 2. According to the findings, family to work enrichment mediates the relationship between boundary integration and life satisfaction (<.001). Furthermore,

the study found that job satisfaction mediates significantly and positively between boundary integration and life satisfaction (<.001). Hence, both mediating hypotheses were also accepted in this research.

Table 4: Indirect Paths.

Indirect Paths	Estimate	Std. error	z-value	p
Boundary Integration→Family to Work Enrichment→Life Satisfaction	0.257	0.06	4.316	< .001
Boundary Integration→Job Satisfaction→Life Satisfaction	0.227	0.049	4.633	< .001

Figure 2: Mediation Analysis.

4. DISCUSSION

The findings of this study confirm the significant impacts of digital and cultural boundaries integration on family-to-work enrichment, job

satisfaction, and life satisfaction among nurses. The primary hypothesis (H1) was that boundary integration has a positive association to life satisfaction, and our results strongly support this. This finding is consistent with the prior work of Aruldoss et al. (2020) who found that satisfaction in different life domains is mutually reinforcing, and with Şimşek Demirbağ and Demirbağ (2022) who found that effective boundary management quality had lessened stress and better overall health. Similarly, Rashmi and Kataria (2021) made significant contributions in the context of COVID-19 forced remote work, by demonstrating that flexible boundary strategies helped improve employees' life satisfaction and established that digital work cultures increased the boundaries experience. Together, the pieces of literature demonstrate a larger contextual description of satisfaction, arguing that satisfaction

in life domains should not only be understood as a fragmented individual outcome, but rather that it too can be understood as a cultural and technological artifact acting upon the generally routinized life.

The following hypothesis (H2) advanced a proposition that the relationship between boundary integration and the level of job satisfaction would be positive, and this was found to be true. Ng *et al.* (2023) reported similar findings where integration strategies were essential for preserving well-being relative to work for any range of professions. Zhang (2025) identified boundary flexibility among midlife employees predicted improved satisfaction relative to the reduction of conflict between work and family. Likewise, Tang *et al.* (2024) emphasized that profiles of digital boundary management predict job satisfaction of healthcare workers. These findings suggest that job satisfaction is increasingly dependent upon boundary integration to effectively manage dual cultural expectations and the digital tools that define modern work practices.

The third hypothesis (H3) contended that boundary integration would exert positive effects on family-to-work enrichment, and the data gave strong support to this hypothesis. The findings strongly resonate with Orellana *et al.* (2023) who hypothesized that transferring resources smoothly across boundaries gives opportunities for enrichment, and with Kunkcu *et al.* (2024), who identified integration by positive spillover as the valence of their research between family and work. Likewise, García-Salirrosas *et al.* (2023) emphasized the role of family support for work performance when, at the same time, family boundaries are permeable. This study suggests, specifically in relation to cultural caregiving obligations and ICT related household accommodations, that boundary integration impacted not only the strength of the effect but reconceptualizes family-to-work enrichment as both emotional, such as positive caregiver trajectories, and structural, such as structural changing accommodations of hybrid work cultures.

The fourth hypothesis (H4) proposed that family-to-work enrichment would be positively related to life satisfaction, and this hypothesis was confirmed. Chughtai (2021) through meta-analysis confirmed that enrichment processes positively contribute to the life consequences of employees regardless of occupation. Similarly, De Gieter *et al.* (2022) found that supportive family-work relations could enhance life satisfaction by reducing emotional exhaustion. Rosa (2022) has contributed to the literature showing that family enrichment for dual-earner couples is

suggested over more digitally intensive roles and, therefore, may be a contributor to well-being. The evidence base is demonstrating that the enrichment's journey has become more complex as families are challenged by digital demands but still support life satisfaction.

The fifth hypothesis (H5) posited a positive relationship between job satisfaction and life satisfaction, and this was validated by the data. This is consistent with Li *et al.* (2021), whose meta-analysis established job satisfaction as a strong predictor of subjective well-being. Similarly, Meng (2022) found that job satisfaction contributes to fulfilling psychological needs that enhance overall happiness, while demonstrated the link among university faculty, showing that satisfaction at work directly shaped life evaluation. In the context of digital healthcare, this relationship is intensified, as nurses' job satisfaction depends not only on traditional support but also on the cultural and ICT-related factors that condition their professional experience.

The sixth hypothesis (H6) proposed that family-to-work enrichment mediates the relationship between boundary integration and life satisfaction, and this mediation was fully supported. Ng *et al.* (2022) previously observed that enrichment mediated flexible work arrangements and turnover intentions, while McDaniel *et al.* (2021) found that enrichment linked workplace support to life satisfaction outcomes. Palumbo *et al.* (2021) further confirmed that enrichment processes reduce stress and enhance satisfaction among healthcare professionals. In the present study, family adjustments to digital workloads such as accommodating telehealth shifts intensified the mediating effect, demonstrating how cultural and technological transformations redefine enrichment.

The seventh hypothesis (H7) proposed that job satisfaction mediates the relationship between boundary integration and life satisfaction, and this was also supported. Michel *et al.* (2022) identified job satisfaction as a bridge linking work experiences to overall well-being, while Mirbabaie and Marx (2024) highlighted that boundary management in nurses influenced job satisfaction and, subsequently, life satisfaction. Choi *et al.* (2022) confirmed that enrichment and satisfaction mediated well-being in hybrid workplaces. The present findings build on these studies by demonstrating that digital workloads and cultural caregiving norms condition how job satisfaction mediates life satisfaction, making the pathway more contextually embedded than previously recognized.

4.1. Theoretical Implications

This study grounds the concept of boundary interaction in the culture and digital environment, thus, making several theoretical contributions to the area of boundary integration. As the first contribution, it delineates the existing literature on boundary theory by showing that the crossing of boundaries is not only a personal matter but also a cultural norms and communication technology (ICT) infrastructure mediated phenomenon. Existing research on boundaries has revealed the preferred ways of dealing with them largely via psychological characteristics, whereas the current study has identified that the factors of managing boundaries such as collectivist values, gender-specific caregiving roles and digital tethering have become more significant.

Second, the findings contribute to the literature on family-to-work enrichment by reconceptualizing the experience as developmentally cultural and technological adaptation. In traditional conceptual frameworks, family-to-work enrichment has been operated strictly to mean emotional support or the transfer of skill from family to work. This study, however, demonstrates how enrichment requires families to adapt to ICT workload demands in digital societies such as irregular online shifts, shared technology. This cultural reframing of enrichment validates the role of households as actors in relation to digital labor form.

Meanwhile, the findings offer significant contributions to research on job satisfaction with a specific focus on hybrid work cultures. In previous models, researchers largely approached job satisfaction as an evaluation of the degree of organizational support or quality of task design. In the present study, however, job satisfaction is also perceived to be contingent upon the degree to which the organization successfully brings ICT tools into the working culture and the cultural expectations managers and other workers employ to conceive of employees' flexibility and availability. This expands the model's theoretical framing by extending job satisfaction to its conceptualization of digital transformation and cultural identity.

Furthermore, this study takes a step beyond by integrating the boundary expansion, family-to-work enrichment, job satisfaction, and life satisfaction as one model to open up the cross-disciplinary insights via the socio-cultural framework that harmonizes the features of organizational psychology, culture studies, and digital sociology. Work satisfaction, by no means, depend merely on the way the place of work is arranged; nevertheless, some well-being aspects may overshadow the workplace arrangement

but still be deeply rooted in the cultural and technological systems that have changed the way work is organized, especially in the 21st century.

4.2. Managerial Implications

The implications of the study need to be considered by hospital administrators as well as policymakers. First, organizations need to understand that managing digital boundaries has become one of the most important elements of employee well-being. Nurses and healthcare workers, in particular, are the individuals in work settings surrounded by ICTs; while electronic health records, telehealth consultations, and digital reporting may be unavoidable, they do contribute to the demands of their work and personal boundaries. A manager should plan not just for a safe workplace but also allow for employees to be trained on the digital tools that, in addition to giving structure, will not overwhelm employees with work and promote healthy boundaries.

Second, the results imply the significance of the emergence of a family-supportive organizational culture. As family-to-work enrichment acts as a mediator for the relationship of boundary integration with life satisfaction, thus, hospitals are to implement policies that support employees in their caregiving roles. Among the flexible scheduling policies that could be used to help employees taking care of their children or parents and the policies that ensure respect for cultural caregiving practices are strategies through which the employees can be assisted to restrict their dual job demands. Essentially, these policies are ways to incorporate well-being, while also promoting retention and commitment to the organization, into a workplace that often has turnover issues.

To sum up, at a larger societal level, the findings support the establishment of policy frameworks that reflect the intersection of cultural norms and digital work. For example, public health and labor policies should acknowledge how collectivist/caring values and gendered work intersect, and how hybrid work is geometrically driving intersectionality, particularly among nurses and nursing-related professions where the majority of the workforce is female. For sustainability, organizations should provide the workplace with cultural and digital infrastructure to reflect ground reality. As a result, public policy can support the re-organization of workforce participation following physical changes to norms.

5. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

While the present study provides important information on how digital and cultural boundary integration is associated with family-to-work

enrichment, job satisfaction, and life satisfaction, there are a few key limitations that should be noted. First, the study's sample was limited to only nurses in Gorakhpur, Uttar Pradesh, India. Although this context is pertinent because it highlights how collectivist norms interact with healthcare practices driven by ICT, the sample cannot necessarily be generalized to all cultural or professional settings. Future studies might strive to expand the analysis into multiple regions and countries, with a focus on how boundary integration may operate in different cultural settings, particularly through comparing collectivist versus individualist societies or societies with varying levels of digital infrastructure.

Second, the study used a cross-sectional survey design, thus limiting inference of causal paths between constructs of interest. Although structural equation modeling suggested evidence of mediation, this analysis does not provide temporal ordering. Longitudinal research would allow researchers to consider how digital

and cultural boundary integration changes over time, particularly with new technological advances or changes in societal norms. Longitudinal research would also provide more definitive evidence for causal paths between boundary integration, enrichment, job satisfaction, and life satisfaction.

Third, the study incorporated measures of the use of ICT and cultural caregiving expectations, however, the survey approach limited the exploration of lived experiences. Future research could utilize qualitative or mixed methods, such as interviews or ethnographies, to more fully explore the ways in which families and workers negotiate the demands of digital daily life and cultural obligation. These approaches would demonstrate the micro-level practices, such as sharing devices or using online content so that work is available during a later shift, or incorporating cultural rituals where parents share aspects of cultural practices to provide enrichment and satisfaction.

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